

Proposed Law: Institutionalizing the Creation of One Strong Political Party in the Philippines

Open to all citizens regardless of social status.

Minimum Requirements:

1. Signed and Notarized Statesman's Affidavit (2025);
2. Self-Imposed Limit on Political Dynasty - Members must commit to not pass positions to legal heirs or spouses, and to not appoint family members in important government positions. Maximum of one politician from the same family members in every election;
3. Mandatory Debate Initiation and Participation Using "Fair Debate Framework with Questions from the Citizens" – so the public can find the best and the brightest, while filtering the ignorant and the incompetent. Equal opportunity to all qualified candidates;
4. Publication of SALN (Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth) with redacted information due to privacy. Submission of SALN is enshrined in the 1987 Constitution;
5. Property Ownership Limitation - Three properties cap with a total lot size not exceeding 1,500 sqm, like any ordinary Filipino citizens. Forcing elected and public officials to realize what it means to live a "modest life" (excess wealth prior to joining the political party shall be used to build public schools and hospitals);
6. Full-Time Position Commitment - All members must treat public office as a full-time job, working 8 a.m. to 5 p.m. like any other public official and private employee, and with a limited vacation/sick leave;
7. Commitment to Implement at Least 80% of the Proposed Laws in The Great Nation 2025. The remaining 20% may be open to public debate, revision, or rejection, acknowledging the possibility of confirmation bias;
8. No Foreign Properties - True public servants invest in the people and the greater good, while the opposite invest in earthly wealth and possessions. There's an opportunity cost of corruption and excessive wealth, as explained in The Great Nation 2025;
9. One Bank Account with Deposit Cap - Recommended 10M, or any amount just enough for retirement. Excess wealth prior to joining the political party shall be used to

build public schools and hospitals; and

10. No Investment in Speculative Assets - Members are banned from investing in stocks, cryptocurrencies, or any asset whose main purpose is appreciation. Again, invest in people and the greater good.

A strong political party, open to all citizens, and far better than those of China, Singapore, Japan, United States, and other European Countries.

It's just a proposed law. Mexico institutionalized a strong political party as early as 1929, and the Soviet Union followed in 1936.

It's already 2025, and we're nearly a century behind.

"A government of the people, by the people, for the people" - Abraham Lincoln